

H2020 - INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP - Leadership in enabling and industrial technologies - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

ICT-14-2016: Big Data PPP: cross-sectorial and cross-lingual data integration and experimentation

**BIG DATA
OCEAN**

BigDataOcean

“Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications”

D8.1 - Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan, Initial Release

Workpackage: WP8 – Dissemination and Communication Activities

Authors:	EXMILE
Status:	Final
Date:	31/03/2017
Version:	1.00
Classification:	Public

Disclaimer:

The BigDataOcean project is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme of the European Union. This document reflects only authors' views. The EC is not liable for any use that may be done of the information contained therein

BigDataOcean Project Profile

Grant Agreement No.: 732310

Acronym:	BigDataOcean
Title:	Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications
URL:	http://www.bigdataocean.eu/site/
Start Date:	01/01/2017
Duration:	30 months

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Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks
0.1	19/01/2017	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE)	ToC
0.2	27/01/2017	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE)	Updated template, moved Measures for evaluation to a new chapter (3)
0.3	07/03/2017	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis, Dimitris Zissis, Argyris Stasinakis (EXMILE), Carlos Agostinho (UNINOVA), Panagiotis Kokkinakos (NTUA), Konstantinos Perakis (UBITECH), Nuno Amaro (NESTER)	First Draft contributions
0.31	08/03/2017	Panagiotis Kokkinakos (NTUA)	NTUA Input and Preliminary Review
0.32	13/03/2017	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE)	Addressing comments, Adding inputs
0.33	14/03/2017	Nuno Amaro (NESTER)	Adding inputs, short review
0.4	17/03/2017	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE), Fabrizio Orlandi (UBONN), Enrico Ferro (ISMB)	Resolving comments, pre-final version
0.5	21/03/2017	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE), Michael Pachnos (ANEK), Fani Panagopoulou (Foinikas), Antonis Chalkiopoulos, Maria Sotiropoulou (HCMR)	Adding inputs
0.51	28/03/2017	Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrou (NTUA)	Internal review comments
0.52	28/03/2017	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE)	Addressing internal review comments
1.00	31/03/2017	Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Dimitrios Askounis (NTUA)	Deliverable finalisation

Executive Summary

This Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan sets out the key steps and activities that will ensure maximum stakeholder engagement and project awareness. The aim is to ensure broad visibility and impact of the project work and results to the wider community of stakeholders while adopting a comprehensive and effective approach to dissemination activities throughout the consortium. The dissemination and communication strategy is defined in three themes, (i) raising awareness about the project, (ii) informing about the results and interacting with the various stakeholders and, finally, (iii) promoting the project throughout the community. This plan is essential for the effective coordination of all initiatives and also for defining the messages which should be targeted towards the different audiences. The dissemination and communication plan is defined from the very beginning of the project but shall be constantly updated throughout the duration of the project.

This document will firstly identify the target audience and stakeholders before outlining the specific strategy. The dissemination channels will be identified and described in relation to specific stakeholder and interest groups. Following this, the specific actions to be implemented in the first 15 months of the project will be outlined, which will include the preparation of promotional material, the project website, participation and organisation of relevant conferences/workshops and others. These are expected to be refined in D8.4, "Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report and Plan for Second Reporting Period" which will be released at the end of M15. Finally, the document will also include a set of standardisation bodies identified as relevant to the project and indicate the preliminary planned activities in relation to those standardisation bodies.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
BDO	BigDataOcean
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
DEIB	Dissemination, Exploitation and Innovation Board
EC	European Commission
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
EDF	European Data Forum
ESS	European Statistical System
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NGO	Non-government Organisation
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
ISO	Organisation for Standardisation
PPP	Public Private Partnership
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SaaS	Software as a Service
TB	Terra Byte
TBD	To Be Decided

1 Introduction

1.1 Project Overview & Objectives

BigDataOcean aims to capitalise on existing modern technological breakthroughs in the areas of the big data driven economy, and roll out a completely new value chain of interrelated data streams coming from diverse sectors and languages and residing on cross technology innovations being delivered in different formats (as well in different states, e.g. structured/unstructured, real-time/batches) in order to revolutionise the way maritime-related industries work, showcasing a huge and realistic economic, societal and environmental impact that is being achieved by introducing an economy of knowledge into a traditional sector which does not operate in an orchestrated manner and is rather fragmented. This infrastructure will be combined with four strong pilots that will bring into BigDataOcean a huge amount of data (in TBs) in order to develop the largest maritime database as a resource of collaborative, data-driven intelligence.

The main objective of BigDataOcean is to enable maritime big data scenarios for EU-based companies, organisations and scientists, through a multi-segment platform that will combine data of different velocity, variety and volume under an inter-linked, trusted, multilingual engine to produce a big-data repository of value and veracity back to the participants and local communities.

Project objectives can be defined across a technical, business and scientific level.

Objective	Description
Technical objective	BigDataOcean will deliver the greatest repository for maritime data to enable big data scenarios; enhance those data with semantic and linked data characteristics to increase their value and make them easily reusable; so that at the end cross-sector and multi-lingual integration will be much easier with less pre-processing.
Business Objective	BigDataOcean will contribute by enabling different stakeholders in a collaborative but also flexible (i.e. between private and public resources) repository for maritime big data and will provide them with the tools (i.e. applications and APIs) to gain business logic capabilities on these data; Thus allow them to make data-driven decisions based on diverse data resources, coming from well-trusted providers; And enable new business models that will secure sustainability and transparency in organisations operations.
Scientific Objective	BigDataOcean will allow scientists to automate many reasoning processes and existing models because of the structural enhancement of big data from different resources; Provide them with the greatest repository of data and allow them focus on building better models and algorithms without caring on finding those data; And reduce the barriers of analysing maritime data, thus giving incentives for running research tasks (i.e. indications of causality) to stakeholders outside the academia (e.g. NGOs, students, local communities, policy makers).

Table 1-1: BigDataOcean objectives as defined at a technical, business and scientific level

1.2 Objective of the document

This Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan sets out the key steps and activities that will ensure maximum stakeholder engagement and project awareness. Throughout this document, dissemination is referred to as the public disclosure of the results of a project across any medium. It is the process of promoting and generating awareness about the project from the very beginning. Its aim is to make the project results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way. Communication refers to taking measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences including the broad public, while engaging in a two-way exchange of information (European Commission, 2016).

The overall goals of this document are:

1. To identify the stakeholders for the BigDataOcean
2. To define specific channels and messages to reach out to these stakeholders and the mechanisms for efficient communications with these groups and the public
3. To define a strategy and activity plan for the engagement of all partners so as to achieve maximum visibility
4. To identify the standardisation and regulation framework that overlaps with BigDataOcean activities

While dissemination efforts are mostly aimed towards disclosure of the results of the project, communication focuses on promoting the action itself. Towards these goals, communication activities are aimed at

- Showing how scientific excellence is achieved and societal challenges are addressed through the EU wide collaboration
- Showing how the scientific outcomes are applicable to everyday challenges
- Improving industry competitiveness

1.3 Structure of the document

The first part of this document introduces the objectives of the project and the dissemination and communication plan.

Following this, the stakeholders and target audience are identified. Stakeholder identification is the first and foremost important task in effective stakeholder engagement and overall user centred system design. Next, the dissemination and communication channels implemented by the consortium will be outlined and defined in relation to the specific stakeholders and groups. A dissemination and communication calendar will assign specific actions to each member of the consortium. All in all, the industrial partners will approach relevant industry sectors, as well as their distributors and client networks, while the academic and research partners will focus on disseminating the project results towards research institutes and universities across Europe. Following this, methods of monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the plan will be defined. Finally, the document at hand lists the standardisation bodies and groups that are relevant to the project's activities.

2 Dissemination and Communication Plan

2.1 Dissemination and communication roles and points of contact

A number of roles are critical for successfully implementing and organising the dissemination and communication strategy. The individuals in these roles are the project spokespersons, tasked with defining the official dissemination strategy and activates for the consortium as a whole, producing communication plans and leading the related activities.

Table 2-1 lists these individuals and their contact details.

Role	Responsibility	Assignee
Project coordinator	This person is in charge of the day-to-day management of the entire project.	Dimitrios Askounis (NTUA)
Dissemination Manager	The Dissemination Manager will coordinate all the communication and dissemination activities of the project.	Dimitrios Zissis (EXMILE)
Exploitation Manager	The Exploitation Manager will coordinate all exploitation activities of the project monitoring progress to guarantee consistency between technical and market choices. He will also coordinate IPR management and conflict resolution.	Enrico Ferro (ISMB)
Work Package 8 leader	The Work Package 8 Leader will coordinate all the activities of Work Package 8 taking all the necessary actions needed for accomplishing all the work packages tasks and delivering all the work packages deliverables in time.	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE)

Table 2-1: Dissemination and communication roles

2.2 The Dissemination, Exploitation and Innovation Board (DEIB)

Building on the importance of dissemination, innovation and exploitation of every innovation action, the Dissemination, Exploitation and Innovation Board (DEIB) will be responsible for the dissemination, exploitation and innovation activities of the BigDataOcean project. It will include representatives by all partners with high expertise in the commercialisation of R&I and in the ICT service delivery market and will operate/meet in project meetings (at least semi-annually), and/or on demand (physically or through conference calls) whenever deemed necessary. DEIB will be responsible for raising public awareness of the project idea; ensuring wide dissemination of the project results; sharing best practices and lessons learnt; identifying innovation potential and developing innovation strategies; maintaining a list of exploitable results; outlining the strategy for knowledge management and protection; agreeing on and

developing the overall exploitation plan; coordinating the development of individual partner exploitation plans; appraising the technology readiness level of the project results; pursuing pre-market strategies for the exploitation of the project results; identifying potential investors that would be interested in further investing on BigDataOcean results and offerings; identifying opportunities in order to ensure the continuation of the project, e.g. through public funding.

Partner	Representative
NTUA	Panagiotis Kokkinakos (pkokkinakos@epu.ntua.gr)
EXMILE	Dimitris Zisis (dzisis@marinetraffic.com)
UBONN	Fabrizio Orlandi (orlandi@iai.uni-bonn.de)
NESTER	Nuno Amaro (nuno.amaro@rdnester.com)
HCMR	Antonis Chalkiopoulos (achalk@hcmr.gr)
UBITECH	Kostas Perakis (kperakis@ubitech.eu)
UNINOVA	Carlos Agostinho (ca@uninova.pt)
ISMB	Enrico Ferro (ferro@ismb.it)
ANEK	Michalis Pachnos (mpachnos@anek.gr)
FOINIKAS	Marie Emmanouilidou (memmanouilidou@fnk.gr)

Table 2-2: Dissemination, Exploitation and Innovation Board members

2.3 Project Spokespersons

To assure high quality and a common communication profile a number of individuals are entitled to speak as project representative in the listed activities. Table 2-3 below includes the project's spokespersons besides the project coordinator and the DEIB.

Partner	Point of contact for dissemination and communication activities
NTUA	Panagiotis Kokkinakos (pkokkinakos@epu.ntua.gr)
EXMILE	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (konstantinos.chatzikokolakis@marinetraffic.com)
UBONN	Fabrizio Orlandi (orlandi@iai.uni-bonn.de)
NESTER	Nuno Amaro (nuno.amaro@rdnester.com)
HCMR	Antonis Chalkiopoulos (achalk@hcmr.gr) Maria Sotiropoulou (marsot@hcmr.gr)
UBITECH	Kostas Perakis (kperakis@ubitech.eu)
UNINOVA	Carlos Agostinho (ca@uninova.pt)
ISMB	Enrico Ferro (ferro@ismb.it) Matteo Ferraris (ferraris@ismb.it)

	Michele Osella (osella@ismb.it)
ANEK	Michalis Pachnos (mpachnos@anek.gr)
FOINIKAS	Fani Panagopoulou (fpanagopoulou@fnk.gr)

Table 2-3: Big Data Ocean spokespersons

2.4 Target Audience

A wide variety of stakeholders is expected to benefit from BigDataOcean services. Starting from the 4 pilots anticipated for deployment in the platform during the project's lifetime, all the candidate types of stakeholders, as well as the specific segments within the stakeholder domain, that are expected to use BigDataOcean services have been identified and are listed below in Table 2-4.

Target Stakeholders	Stakeholder Segments
A – End-Users	Enterprises, entrepreneurs, NGOs, policy makers that are part of the big data and maritime industry domains.
B – IT Industry Players	IT companies, web entrepreneurs, software engineers of solutions for big data and maritime domains
C – Industry Associations & Technology Clusters	European initiatives and clusters (like BDVA and FIWARE), research communities, associations, federations (like IMS, EFFRA, IFIP, IEEE, NEM)
D – H2020 Programme Stakeholders	Participants, project partners and relevant stakeholders active in the H2020 projects
E – Researchers and Adademia	Individuals engaged in research initiatives and/or working in research/academic institutes
F - Policy Makers & Standardisation Organisations	Policy-makers at any level like EC Directorates and Units, Ministries and Governments, Regulatory Agencies, Standardisation Organisations (CEN, ISO, ETSI, etc.)
G – General Public	Civil society representatives, general public and anyone interested in the project

Table 2-4: Stakeholders' categories and segments

Following this, stakeholders have been identified in relation to each pilot scenario.

Big Data Ocean Pilot	Business Segments
PILOT 1 – FAULT PREDICTION AND PROACTIVE MAINTENANCE	Ship builders, ship owners, ship managers, maritime equipment constructors, shipyards, maritime surveyors, ship classification societies, charterers, marine engineers.

PILOT 2 – MARE PROTECTION	Coast Guard, Emergency response companies, Shipping companies, Oil Companies, Port Authorities, Research and Educational Units, Public and Governmental entities, Navy
PILOT 3 – MARITIME SECURITY AND ANOMALY DETECTION	Ship Builders; Ship Owners and Managers; Freight Forwarders and Logistics Companies, Coast Guard, Border Control, Police and Maritime Security Authorities; Charterers and Cargo Consignees; Port Authorities and operators; Shippers; Maritime Surveyors; Pilots, Tug operators, Towage and Salvage Companies; Search & Rescue Authorities
PILOT 4 – WAVE POWER AS THE NEXT CLEAN ENERGY SOURCE	Wave energy promoters, utilities, consulting companies, national energy authorities, national maritime authorities, port authorities and operators, tug operators.

Table 2-5: Stakeholders' relation to pilots

2.5 Stakeholders' and Users' Engagement activities

BigDataOcean will organise a set of activities that will strengthen the link with end users and stakeholders. In February 2017, the project partners organised four workshops, one per pilot, to communicate to stakeholders the project's objective and proposed solution and help BigDataOcean partners understand the requirements of each pilot scenario. Three of the workshops were hosted at Athens, Greece and one at Caparica, Portugal. During the workshops BigDataOcean partners had the opportunity to have some fruitful discussions with maritime stakeholders and exchange invaluable information related to the pilots. The organisers provided questionnaires to the stakeholders to build knowledge regarding stakeholders' needs and identify how their interactions outline the Maritime Data Value Chain. In addition, project partners triggered remote conversations with ship builders, ship owners, port authorities, tug operators and other stakeholders when attending the workshop was not feasible, maximising the potential audience of the workshop and leading thus to successful events.

2.6 Dissemination and Communication Channels

2.6.1 Theme and key messages

Themes and key messages provide short descriptions of the project, its vision and objectives to be used during communication activities. The messages have been agreed upon by all partners and provide the framework for any promotional speeches, presentations, and interactions.

Theme	Description
Summary	BigDataOcean aims to capitalise on existing modern technological breakthroughs in the areas of the big data driven economy, and roll out a completely new value chain of interrelated data streams coming from diverse sectors and languages and residing on cross technology

	innovations being delivered in different formats (as well in different states, e.g. structured/unstructured, real-time/batches) in order to revolutionise the way maritime-related industries work, showcasing a huge and realistic economic, societal and environmental impact that is being achieved by introducing an economy of knowledge into a traditional sector which does not operate in an orchestrated manner and is rather fragmented. This infrastructure will be combined with four strong pilots that will bring into BigDataOcean a huge amount of data (in TBs) in order to develop the largest maritime database as a resource of collaborative, data-driven intelligence. BigDataOcean will give participants the capability to upload both private and public resources of data, and interrelate them over public and private queries and diagrams.
Vision	BigDataOcean envisions to become the solution that will disrupt the maritime business sector through the effective exploitation of cross-sectorial and multi-lingual big data towards innovative analytics, knowledge, business intelligence and service delivery.
Main Objective	The main objective of BigDataOcean is to enable maritime big data scenarios for EU-based companies, organisations and scientists, through a multi-segment platform that will combine data of different velocity, variety and volume under an inter-linked, trusted, multilingual engine to produce a big-data repository of value and veracity back to the participants and local communities.
Technical Objective	In the technical level, BigDataOcean will deliver the greatest repository for maritime data to enable big data scenarios; enhance those data with semantic and linked data characteristics to increase their value and make them easily reusable; so that at the end cross-sector and multi-lingual integration will be much easier with less pre-processing.
Business Objective	In the business level, BigDataOcean will contribute by enabling different stakeholders in a collaborative but also flexible (i.e. between private and public resources) repository for maritime big data, BigDataOcean will provide them with the tools (i.e. applications and APIs) to gain business logic capabilities on these data; Thus help them to make data-driven decisions based on diverse data resources, coming from well-trusted providers; And enable new business models that will secure sustainability and transparency in organisations' operations.
Scientific Objective	In the scientific Level, BigDataOcean will allow scientists to automate many reasoning processes and existing models because of the structural enhancement of big data from different resources; Provide them with the greatest repository of data and allow them focus on building better models and algorithms without caring on finding those data; And reduce the barriers of analysing maritime data, thus giving incentives for running research tasks (i.e. indications of causality) to stakeholders outside the academia (e.g. NGOs, students, local communities, policy makers)
Key message	Exploiting oceans of data for maritime applications

Table 2-6: Themes and key messages

In accordance to H2020 guidelines all dissemination and communication activities must acknowledge EU funding. All BigDataOcean communication and dissemination material will contain a message stating ***"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 732310."***

2.6.2 Project Identity

A key communication element, necessary for coherent and effective stakeholder interaction and building project awareness is the project identity. This often plays a critical role in dissemination and networking as it helps shape the audiences' first impressions about the project. For this reason, from early on in the project, attention was paid in the design of a project logo, the creation of a set of promotional materials and the deployment of a project website. Also, a toolkit (presentation and document templates) was set up, for all partners to use when communicating project information; new and updates.

2.6.2.1 Logo and graphic identity

A project's logo is an important asset and a tool for communication and dissemination activities. It supports visually triggered memory recognition of a user's relationship with a tangible or intangible system, service or product. A successful logo is a visual manifestation of a projects outcomes in a specific stakeholder community. Our main goal was the project's logo would be representative of all partners' expectations of the project. The logo selection was a survey selection process among a number of candidate images depicted in Figure 2-1 below.

Figure 2-1: Candidate Logos

After this process, the logo selected was the one that seemed to more accurately convey the message of “Analysing an ocean of data”. Figure 2-2 depicts the selected logo for the project.

Figure 2-2: Big Data Ocean selected logo

2.6.3 Media kit

A general presentation of the project based on 14 slides has been produced for the use and re-use by the partners. The presentation briefly introduces the scope, the concept and the technical challenges of the project, the involved partners, the identified pilots, expected impact and the target users.

2.6.4 BigDataOcean leaflet

Figure 2-3 and Figure 2-4 below present the graphic design of the project’s leaflet. The aim of this leaflet is to communicate the project’s key message and attract users’ and stakeholders interest. During the project’s lifetime, additional leaflets with material driven from the project’s achievements will be produced.

Stakeholders and user communities

BigDataOcean is targeted towards all possible stakeholders involved in maritime applications. Ship builders, ship owners and managers, freight forwarders and logistics companies, tug operators, charterers and cargo consignees, public authorities (e.g. coast guard, border control, police and maritime security authorities) and NGOs (e.g. search and rescue authorities) are just some examples of stakeholders that will benefit from the BigDataOcean services.

Exploiting oceans of data for maritime applications

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Social

- twitter.com/big_data_ocean
- [www.facebook.com/Big-Data- Ocean-1860577064227045](https://www.facebook.com/Big-Data-Ocean-1860577064227045)
- www.linkedin.com/groups/13505618

BigDataOcean aims to provide a multi-segment platform that combines data of different velocity, variety and volume using an inter-linked, trusted, multilingual engine.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 732110.

Figure 2-3: Big Data Ocean leaflet (back and front page)

Figure 2-4: Big Data Ocean leaflet (pages inside)

2.6.5 Website and Online Media

The project’s website is up and running since the 1st month of the project. The figure below shows the content presented at the home page of the project (i.e. <http://www.bigdataocean.eu/site/>).

Figure 2-5: Big Data Ocean website homepage

As depicted in the figure, besides the home page, news, events, newsletter and “contact us” are also available at the website’s menu. Figure 2-6 and Figure 2-7 depict the content of the news and event

pages (as captured on 06/03/2017). Events page lists all the events that are organised by the project partners and the ones that projects partners have attended (e.g. Networking and Info Days organised by the European Commission, workshops, conferences, etc.). News page includes all the news that are considered relevant to the project. Finally, it is noted that the homepage includes a link to the project's private area, where username/password are requested from the site in order to authorise access to restricted material to the user.

Figure 2-6: Big Data Ocean website events page

Figure 2-7: Big Data Ocean website news page

2.6.6 Scientific Conferences and Tradeshows

The Dissemination work package will ensure that BigDataOcean results are communicated through dedicated presentations, publications, participation in and organisation of workshops and conferences. Table 2-7 below presents a list of candidate conferences for submitting scientific papers with BigDataOcean results.

Conference	Site	Type
BDCloud 2017: The 7th IEEE International Conference on Big Data and Cloud Computing	http://bdcloud.csclouds.org	Research
DATA 2017	http://www.dataconference.org/	Research
ICCBDC 2017: International Conference on Cloud and Big Data Computing (ICCBDC 2017)	http://www.iccbdc.org/	Research/Industry
CBDCom 17- IEEE International Conference on Cloud and Big Data Computing	http://iee-smartworld.org/2017/cbdcom/	Research
Innovate-Data 2017: The 3rd International Conference on Big Data Innovations and Applications	http://www.ficloud.org/innovate-data-2017/	Research/Industry/Policy/Practitioners
BigDAW 2017: International Workshop on Big Data Analytics	https://www.zurich.ibm.com/BigDataAnalytics/	Research/Industry
DSAA 2017: The 4th IEEE International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics 2017	http://www.dslab.it.aoyama.ac.jp/dsaa2017/	Research/Industry/Practitioners
IEEE BigDataService 2017: THE THIRD IEEE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON BIG DATA COMPUTING SERVICE AND APPLICATIONS	http://big-dataservice.net	Research
VLDB 2017 International Conference on Very Large Data Bases	http://www.vldb.org/2017/	Research/Industry

Conference	Site	Type
ICE IEEE ITM 2017 The 23 rd ICE/IEEE International Technology Management Conference	http://www.ice-conference.org/	Research/Industry/Governmental organisations
IISA 2017: 8 th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications	http://iisa2017.unipi.gr	Research/Industry
IEEE IRI 2017 IEEE International Conference on Information Reuse and Integration	http://www.sis.pitt.edu/iri2017/index.html	Research/Practitioners/Industry/Government
IEEE BigDATA	http://www.ieeebigdata.org/2017/	Research/Industry
International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC)	http://iswc2017.semanticweb.org/	Research
Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC)	http://2017.eswc-conferences.org/	Research
MTS/IEEE OCEANS (e.g., OCEANS 2016)	http://www.ieee.org/conferences_events/conferences/conferencedetails/index.html?Conf_ID=31204	Research
ACM SIGMOD/PODS conference (SIGMOD 2017)	http://sigmod2017.org/	Research
International Conference on Extending Database Technology	http://edbticdt2017.unive.it/	Research/Practitioners
OnTheMove Federated Conferences & Workshops	http://www.otmconferences.org	Research/Industry
International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems (ICEIS)	http://www.iceis.org	Research/Practitioners
International Symposium on Model-driven Approaches for Simulation Engineering	http://www.sel.uniroma2.it/mo4sim17/	Research/Practitioners
Advanced Doctoral Conference on Computing, Electrical and Industrial Systems (DoCEIS'17)	http://sites.uninova.pt/doceis	Research
European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC)	http://www.ewtec.org/	Research/Industry/Practitioners

Conference	Site	Type
SMARTGREENS (International Conference on Smart Grids and Green ICT Systems)	http://www.smartgreens.org/	Research/Industry/Practitioners
IEEE Green Tech (Annual Green Technologies Conference)	http://ieeegreentech.org/	Research/Industry/Policy/Practitioners

Table 2-7: List of scientific conferences and tradeshow

2.6.7 Scientific Journals

Similarly to the previous subsection, several journals have either common topics with the concept of the project or are expected to publish special issue with a relevant topic. The following table lists the details of all the candidate journals where BigDataOcean partners can submit scientific achievements of the project.

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
Elsevier	Energy Policy	Energy Policy is an international peer-reviewed journal addressing the policy implications of energy supply and use from their economic, social, planning and environmental aspects.
Elsevier	Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments	The world must move toward a more sustainable energy future, and the development of technologies that facilitate this for transport, heating, and power systems is crucial. This journal encourages papers on any aspect and scale of technologies for energy generation and/or utilisation that decrease the impact of that production and use, from the laboratory to commercial applications.
IEEE	IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy	The IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy is a cross disciplinary and internationally archival journal aimed at disseminating results of research on sustainable energy that relates to, arises from, or deliberately influences energy generation, transmission, distribution and delivery.

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
Taylor & Francis	Enterprise Information Systems	Enterprise Information Systems (EIS) is a world-leading journal focusing on both the technical and applications aspects of EIS technology, and the complex and cross-disciplinary problems of enterprise integration that arise in integrating extended enterprises in a contemporary global supply chain environment.
Elsevier	International Journal of Marine Energy	International Journal of Marine Energy will aim to publish original, high quality papers covering fundamental and applied research as well as case studies relevant to renewable energy emanating from the marine or ocean environment with particular focus on wave and tidal energy. The Journal focuses on wave and tidal topics including: fundamental understanding; fluid mechanics; design; modelling and optimisation of devices and arrays/ farms; environmental assessment; design codes; regulations; policy; economics; monitoring; planning evaluation; legislation and legal aspects related to sustainable exploitation of the ocean and tidal resources. Papers on tidal lagoons as well as cross cutting topics of relevance to wave and tidal energy such as structures, platforms and electrical connections are also welcomed.
Springer	Special Issue on Environmental and Geospatial Data Analytics -	Environmental and more generally geospatial information

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
	International Journal of Data Science and Analytics	<p>is now provided by crowdsourcing but also by public administrations in the context of the open data policies. Analyses of such data are still challenging because of their heterogeneity (structural, semantic, spatial and temporal) and because of the difficulty in choosing the "best" knowledge discovery process to apply, according to the needs of the experts in the field. This special issue aims to provide high quality research covering all or part of the challenges mentioned above, from a theoretical or experimental point of view. Challenge about data science deals with creation, storage, search, sharing, modelling, analysis, and visualisation of data, information, and knowledge. In Data Science context, spatio-temporal aspects are crucial in order to manage and mine data, to index and retrieve information, and finally to discover and visualise knowledge.</p> <p>By taking into account these spatio-temporal aspects, original methods have to be proposed for processing real and complex data from different domains, e.g., environment, agriculture, health, urban, and so forth.</p>
Elsevier	SI Spatiotemporal Big Data/ FGCS	This special issue aims to highlight problems originating

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
		<p>from real world application fields dealing with spatiotemporal Big Data challenges and invite researchers working towards novel methods for addressing these issues to submit their work. The aim of this special issue publication is to cover novel data science theory and algorithms, data engineering and real world systems architectures, which are aimed at the storage, fusion, processing, learning and ultimately knowledge extraction from real world spatio-temporal datasets.</p>
IOS Press	Semantic Web Journal	<p>The journal Semantic Web – Interoperability, Usability, Applicability (published and printed by IOS Press, ISSN: 1570-0844), in short Semantic Web journal, brings together researchers from various fields which share the vision and need for more effective and meaningful ways to share information across agents and services on the future internet and elsewhere. As such, Semantic Web technologies shall support the seamless integration of data, on-the-fly composition and interoperation of Web services, as well as more intuitive search engines. The semantics – or meaning – of information, however, cannot be defined without a context, which makes personalisation,</p>

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
		trust, and provenance core topics for Semantic Web research. New retrieval paradigms, user interfaces, and visualisation techniques have to unleash the power of the Semantic Web and at the same time hide its complexity from the user. Based on this vision, the journal welcomes contributions ranging from theoretical and foundational research over methods and tools to descriptions of concrete ontologies and applications in all areas. We especially welcome papers which add a social, spatial, and temporal dimension to Semantic Web research, as well as application-oriented papers making use of formal semantics.
Elsevier	Computers & Geosciences	Computers & Geosciences publishes high impact, original research at the interface between Computer Sciences and Geosciences. Publications should apply modern computer science paradigms, whether computational or informatics-based, to address problems in the geosciences.
Springer	Earth Science Informatics	ESIN will help to develop and shape the new field of Earth Science Informatics. It is intended to provide a dissemination platform for research using systems-based approaches to solve multi-scale Earth science problems by encouraging the development

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
		of robust formal and computational models and information systems.
Taylor & Francis	International Journal of Digital Earth	Digital Earth is a virtual representation of the planet, encompassing all its systems and forms, both natural environment and human societies, manifested as a multi-dimensional, multi-scale, multi-temporal, and multi-layer information facility. Digital Earth is the framework for geographically linked research and applications in the physical and social domains of the Earth, a digital modeling platform to monitor, measure, and forecast natural and human activity on the planet, and a visualisation of the world. It is three-dimensional, four-dimensional if a temporal monitoring component is added, and even five-dimensional if scale is treated as a variable instead of a set of discrete steps. As a global initiative, Digital Earth aims to improve social conditions, protect the environment, and support future sustainable development.
Fisheries and Marine Institute	The Journal of Ocean Technology	The Journal of Ocean Technology is a peer-reviewed, open access periodical published by the Fisheries and Marine Institute of Memorial University of Newfoundland. It is designed to cater to all segments of the global ocean

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
		<p>technology community. Its mission is to expand global knowledge and understanding of ocean technologies, to serve as the medium for publishing world-leading research, and to promote innovation that contributes to responsible ocean utilisation and management.</p>
IGI Global	International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems	<p>The International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems (IJSWIS) promotes a knowledge transfer channel where academics, practitioners, and researchers can discuss, analyse, criticise, synthesise, communicate, elaborate, and simplify the more-than-promising technology of the semantic Web in the context of information systems. The journal aims to establish value-adding knowledge transfer and personal development channels in three distinctive areas: academia, industry, and government.</p>
IEEE	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering	<p>The scope includes the knowledge and data engineering aspects of computer science, artificial intelligence, electrical engineering, computer engineering, and other appropriate fields. This Transactions provides an international and interdisciplinary forum to communicate results of new developments in knowledge</p>

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
		<p>and data engineering and the feasibility studies of these ideas in hardware and software. Specific areas to be covered are as follows: Fields and Areas of Knowledge and Data Engineering: (a) Knowledge and data engineering aspects of knowledge based and expert systems, (b) Artificial Intelligence techniques relating to knowledge and data management, (c) Knowledge and data engineering tools and techniques, (d) Distributed knowledge base and database processing, (e) Real-time knowledge bases and databases, (f) Architectures for knowledge and data based systems, (g) Data management methodologies, (h) Database design and modeling, (i) Query, design, and implementation languages, (j) Integrity, security, and fault tolerance, (k) Distributed database control, (l) Statistical databases, (m) System integration and modeling of these systems, (n) Algorithms for these systems, (o) Performance evaluation of these algorithms, (p) Data communications aspects of these systems, (q) Applications of these systems.</p>
Elsevier	Computers in Industry	The aim of Computers in Industry is to publish original, high-quality, application-oriented research papers that show new trends in and options for the use of Information and

Publisher	Journal's topic	Description
		Communication Technology in industry; link or integrate different technology fields in the broad area of computer applications for industry; link or integrate different application areas of ICT in industry.

Table 2-8: List of scientific journals

2.6.8 Press releases and newsletters

Big Data Ocean project has set up a newsletter page where users can subscribe and receive updates and news from the project. Figure 2-8 below depicts the subscription page, which prompts the user to submit some information related to its business activities and help the project to disseminate its main achievements.

The screenshot shows a web page for subscribing to a mailing list. The main heading is 'Subscribe' in blue. Below it is a blue call-to-action text: 'Subscribe to our mailing list to keep up with the news and updates of the BigDataOcean (but also express your interest to get involved!)'. To the right of this text is a small asterisk and the text '* indicates required'. The form contains the following fields: 'Email Address *' (text input), 'First Name' (text input), 'Last Name' (text input), 'Country *' (dropdown menu), 'Industry/Core Activity *' (dropdown menu), 'Pilot interest *' (dropdown menu), and 'How can Big data ocean benefit your line of work?' (text input). A blue 'Subscribe' button is located below the form. On the right side of the page, there is a 'Recent Posts' section with a list of article titles: 'Workshop on maritime security and anomaly detection', 'Running a Prototyping Sprint with BigDataOcean', 'BigDataOcean at the "Information and Networking Days Big Data PPP" event in Luxembourg', 'Kickoff meeting overview.', and 'Big data ocean kickoff meeting'. There is also a small blue icon with a white 'f' and 'in' on the right side of the page.

Figure 2-8: Big Data Ocean website subscription page

To communicate its achievements, establish links and grow synergies with stakeholders, the project is expected to publish a set of e-newsletters. Particularly for the 1st period, BigDataOcean aims to produce 1 newsletter per 3 months. In addition, the project will disseminate its achievements through press releases.

2.7 Dissemination and communication activities

2.7.1 Dissemination Plan and Calendar

BigDataOcean partners have setup a dissemination plan from the first day of the project. This includes participation at fora, workshops and conferences through scientific publications, invited talks, demos, etc. Furthermore, the project has organised a set of workshops (i.e. one workshop for each of the four pilots) so as to bring together all the related stakeholders, introduce the projects' concept, identify their needs and initiate fruitful discussions related to the projects' topics. Table 2-9 below highlights the

dissemination plan and calendar of BigDataOcean for the 1st period of the project. However, this list may be further extended during the project, as new dissemination opportunities may arise.

Partner	Dissemination Activity	Milestone	Month and Location
NTUA (organiser)		Kick-off meeting	M00, Athens Greece
EXMILE	Participation at European Shipping Week	Raise awareness	M02, Brussels Belgium
EXMILE	Project's news and activities	Web site and Blog Social media channels	M03
UNINOVA, NTUA	Organisation of 4 workshops (i.e. one per pilot) with relevant stakeholders	Stakeholders' needs identification, Data Value chain integration	M03, Athens Greece and Caparica Portugal
EXMILE	Participation at BDVA General Assembly meeting	Raising awareness	M03, Brussels Belgium
ISMB (organiser)		1st plenary meeting of the consortium	M04, Turin Italy
UNINOVA	Scientific publication at International Symposium on Model-driven Approaches for Simulation Engineering		M04, Virginia Beach USA
UNINOVA, NESTER	Participation at Advanced Doctoral Conference on Computing, Electrical and Industrial Systems (DoCEIS'17)		M05, Caparica Portugal
UNINOVA (organiser)		2nd plenary meeting of the consortium	M06, Madeira Portugal
All	Scientific publications at IEEE ICE ITM conference		M06, Madeira Portugal
NTUA (Project coordinator), All (presentations and other material)		1st project review meeting	M15

Table 2-9: Dissemination plan and calendar

2.7.2 Blog and Social Media

2.7.2.1 Social Media accounts

BigDataOcean has established a set of social media accounts so as to maximise the visibility of the project and optimise the communication with the user communities which are linked to the project's achievements. In the following subsections, we briefly provide a description of those accounts and the benefits the project is expecting from each one of them.

2.7.2.1.1 Twitter

A Twitter account¹, depicted in Figure 2-9 below, has established for the BigDataOcean from the early beginning of the project (i.e., January 2017) to facilitate a global communication in a measurable and inexpensive manner, and to make use of this fast and straightforward way to communicate with stakeholders, also at conferences, workshops and seminars. This medium is being used to reach out to a broader community making use of the Twitter snowball effect, to share news and thoughts on ongoing research and other findings in the project, and to follow interesting conversations and be part of them. Over the first three months of the project, BigDataOcean posted 12 tweets, has 44 followers and follows 7 people on Twitter.

The use of Twitter is expected to be intensified over the next period so as to communicate upcoming events (e.g. the ICE conference), inform on software releases, share interesting readings and address the audience with questions to gather input on some of the key issues covered by the project.

The use of Twitter is also expected to be beneficial for the acquisition of new subscribers to the project's newsletter, as newsletter feed will be followed by a tweet which directs the audience to the newsletter and the subscription form.

Figure 2-9: Big Data Ocean twitter account

2.7.2.1.2 Facebook

BigDataOcean created a Facebook page², depicted in Figure 2-10 below, to increase the visibility and the communication means of the project. This medium is being used to reach out a broader community through posting project's news, activities and key findings. BigDataOcean's posts at the Facebook page will be usually redirecting to news/activities posted in the project's website, linking thus the facebook

¹ https://twitter.com/big_data_ocean

² https://twitter.com/big_data_ocean

page to content posted in the project's website. BigDataOcean has made 9 posts to the page, has 18 followers and 16 likes, over the first three months of the project.

Figure 2-10: Big Data Ocean facebook page

2.7.2.1.3 Linkedin

BigDataOcean has set up a group on the LinkedIn³ social media platform depicted in Figure 2-11 below. This channel is not the main focus with regards to dissemination but rather used to trigger discussions with our stakeholder communities that frequently use this medium. Thus, our LinkedIn group acts as a portal through which people can find a link to the project website and further request information to the project's activities. During the first three months of BigDataOcean, 16 members have joined the project's group at LinkedIn.

Figure 2-11: Big Data Ocean LinkedIn group

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13505618>

2.7.2.2 Blog and Social Media Plan

In order to keep stakeholders' and users' interest as high as possible, BigDataOcean will post news and updates at its website and at social media. Table 2-10 below captures the way BigDataOcean partners will be active in communicating project's achievements. It should be mentioned that the table includes the minimum number of posts scheduled and as the project progresses additional posts at social media and/or at the project's website are possible.

Partner	Blog Post theme	Indicative Date
EXMILE	Kick-off meeting	M00
ANEK	Announcing project start in ANEK's website	M01
Foinikas	Announcing project's start in AVIN's Internationals site	M01
NTUA	Prototyping session	M02
EXMILE	Pilot workshop	M02
NTUA	Pilot workshop (2 posts, one per pilot)	M03
NESTER	Pilot Workshop in Portugal	M03
UBONN	Data management challenges in BDO	M03
NESTER	Wave Energy (Current status in Europe, short description)	M04
EXMILE	Big Data Ocean plenary meeting	M04
UBITECH	Platform architecture and design	M06
UNINOVA	Meeting and workshop	M06
HCMR	Pilot description and updates	M07
ANEK	Pilot description and updates	M08
UBONN	TBD	M09
Nester	Pilot description	M10
Ubitech	BDO Platform 1st major release	M10
ANEK	Update on Pilot progress	M11
Foinikas	Update on Pilot progress	M11
UNINOVA	TBD	M12
ISMB	TBD	M12
Ubitech	Platform Architecture revisions & APIs	M13
EXMILE	BigDataOcean Review	M15

Table 2-10: Blog and social media posting strategy

2.7.3 Societies and Organisations

BigDataOcean partners have identified a set of societies and organisations relevant to the project's concept and have already participated in events to raise awareness and trigger discussions that will be helpful for the project's success.

2.7.3.1 Identified societies and organisations

BigDataOcean is part of the cluster of projects implementing the contractual Big Data Value Public-Private Partnership (BDV PPP). Thus, BigDataOcean partners have joined the **Big Data Value**

Association (BDVA), which is the private counterpart to the EU Commission to implement the BDV PPP programme. BDVA has over 150 members all over Europe with a well-balanced composition of large and small and medium-sized industries as well as research organisations. BigDataOcean partners will contribute to the BDV PPP activities and participate in relevant events, consultations and match-making events organised in the context of the BDV PPP. Since the collection of up-to-date sectorial data is of crucial importance in view of measuring the success of the PPP, BigDataOcean will provide input in surveys and questionnaires about the BDV PPP.

Furthermore, BigDataOcean intends to contribute to the **European Data Forum** (EDF) which is a meeting place for industry, research, policymakers and community initiatives to discuss the challenges of Big Data and the emerging Data Economy and to develop suitable action plans for addressing these challenges.

2.7.3.2 *Implemented activities*

Big Data Value Association Activity Group meeting

BigDataOcean partners have joined the Big Data Value Association and attended the Activity Group meeting in Brussels on 14-15/03/2017. During the meeting the BigDataOcean dissemination manager presented the project and had the opportunity to meet and exchange ideas with other stakeholders relevant to transportation, energy, etc.

Figure 2-12: BigDataOcean dissemination manager presenting the project during BDVA meeting in Brussels

Information and Networking Days for Big Data PPP

BigDataOcean was invited to attend the H2020 "Information and Networking Days Big Data PPP" event in Luxembourg on 17-18/01/2017. The BigDataOcean coordinator was invited to present the project, while other representatives of the consortium had the opportunity to liaise with the other projects in the PPP cluster, and to meet the candidate proposers for the 2017 call, in view of networking and exchanging ideas.

Figure 2-13: BigDataOcean coordinator presenting the project during H2020 “Information and Networking Days Big Data PPP” event in Luxembourg

2.7.4 Linked Projects and established synergies

Table 2-11 summarises the identified linked projects. BigDataOcean aims to maximise the synergies with related projects and for the 1st period of the project the aim is to reach out to the corresponding spokespersons of those projects and seek for synergies such as joint workshop organisation, etc.

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
datACRON	datACRON is a research and innovation collaborative project introducing novel methods for threat and abnormal activity detection in very large fleets of moving entities spread across large geographical areas. Specifically, datACRON aims to develop novel methods for real-time detection and prediction of trajectories and important events related to moving entities, together with advanced visual	UNIVERSITY OF PIRAEUS RESEARCH CENTER	Prof. George Vouros Dept of Digital Systems

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>analytics methods, over multiple heterogeneous, voluminous, fluctuating, and noisy data streams from moving entities, correlating them with archived data expressing, among others, entities' characteristics, geographical information, mobility patterns, regulations and intentional data (e.g. planned routes), in a timely manner. Technological developments are validated and evaluated in user-defined challenges focusing on increasing the safety, efficiency and economy of operations concerning moving entities in the Air-Traffic Management and Maritime domains. The datACRON project brings together partners from academia and industry to develop the aforementioned novel methods, together with user and data-provision partners from the two domains, in close relation to user-interest groups, focusing on real-life, industrial and</p>		

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>user-defined challenges concerning operations (e.g. surveillance, forecasting of trajectories, characterisation, etc.) regarding moving entities in sea and air.</p>		
AEGIS	<p>AEGIS, brings together the data, the network and the technologies to create a curated, semantically enhanced, interlinked and multilingual repository for public and personal safety-related big data. It delivers a data-driven innovation that expands over multiple business sectors and takes into consideration structured, unstructured and multilingual datasets, rejuvenates existing models and facilitates organisations in the Public Safety and Personal Security linked sectors to provide better and personalised services to their users. AEGIS will introduce new business models through the breed of an open ecosystem of innovation and data sharing principles. From the technology</p>	FRAUNHOFER FOKUS	NTUA

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>perspective, AEGIS targets to revolutionise semantic technologies in big data, big data analytics and visualisations as well as security and privacy frameworks by addressing current challenges and requirements of cross-domain and multilingual applications.</p>		
PREDMINE	<p>Entitled "A Predictive Analytics Platform Using Live Big Data", PREDMINE project is about a new platform that brings the advantages of predictive analytics and big data processing to the financial and insurance sector. The goal is to simplify the application of complex machine learning, pattern recognition and data mining techniques in risk management implementing a platform that helps insurance organisations to estimate risk, thus having competitive advantages in terms of cost, customer relationships (customer satisfaction), and market leadership. The product provides a</p>	PEC ENTERPRISES S.A.	European Affairs Dept.

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>complete collaborative predictive analytics solution supporting (a) state of the art machine learning and classification algorithms based on existing open source libraries (like Apache Mahout, R), (b) automatic data extraction and text mining techniques, as well as (c) big data manipulation and management based on the Hadoop execution environment. This ground-breaking solution enables the existing insurance company's IT personnel to build predictive models and score those models with huge datasets.</p>		
AREA	<p>Entitled "Design, Development & Promotion of an Innovative Business Intelligence Big Data Analytics Platform for Market Research", AREA project targeted at organisations and companies from the entire spectrum of business activities in Greece and international markets, focusing primarily in the mature markets of North America,</p>	PEC ENTERPRISES S.A.	European Affairs Dept.

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>providing the following basic business solutions: - Profile building, - Business intelligence, - Creation, Management and Statistical Analysis of big data, - Modular Structure, - Ability to react with flexibility to the specific needs of the supported businesses (e.g. SaaS, installation and customisation services etc.). The development was based firstly, on the need for exploiting open standards to ensure interconnectivity with existing or non-user systems, and the ability to provide the service through multichannel solutions and secondly the multiplicity of characteristics and needs of potential users of the new service.</p>		
NOBEL GRID	<p>Entitled "New cost-efficient business models for flexible Smart grids", NOBEL GRID will provide advanced tools and ICT services to all actors in the Smart Grid and retail electricity market in order to ensure benefits from cheaper prices, more secure</p>	ETRA INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO SA	UNINOVA

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>and stable grids and clean electricity. NOBEL GRID will provide the necessary tools and mechanisms for real-time monitoring and big data analytics performed over data streams flowing from the different demand end-points of the distribution electrical grid. It will allow for the definition, at individual and aggregated levels, of load flexibility analysis and forecasting, consumers preferences information and other correlated information.</p>		
C2NET	<p>Entitled "Cloud Collaborative Manufacturing Networks", the goal is the creation of a cloud-enabled tools for supporting the supply network optimisation of manufacturing and logistic assets based on collaborative demand, production and delivery plans. C2NET Project will provide a scalable real-time architecture, platform and software to allow the supply network partners: to master complexity and data security of the supply network, to store</p>	ATOS IT SOLUTIONS AND SERVICES SRO	UNINOVA

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>product, process and logistic data, to optimise the manufacturing assets by the collaborative computation of production plans, to optimise the logistics assets through efficient delivery plans and to render the complete set of supply chain management information on the any digital mobile device (PC, tablets, smartphones, etc.) of decision makers enabling them to monitor, visualise, control, share and collaborate.</p> <p>The Project results will be: i) the C2NET Data Collection Framework for IoT-based continuous data collection from supply network resources; ii) the C2NET Optimiser for the optimisation of manufacturing and logistics assets of the supply network by the collaborative computation of production, replenishment and delivery plans; iii) the C2NET Collaboration Tools for providing support to the</p>		

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>collaborative processes of the supply network, and iv) the C2NET Cloud Platform (C2NET CPL) to integrate the data module, the optimisers and the collaborative tools in the cloud.</p>		
AQUASMART	<p>The AQUASMART (Aquaculture Smart and Open Data Analytics as a Service) project responds to the EU's Blue Growth Strategy for marine and maritime sustainable growth and the Commission's Europe 2020 Strategy. Aquaculture industry, which comprises mainly of SME companies, represents a significant source of protein for people. Globally, nearly half the fish consumed by humans is produced by fish farms. Global production is forecasted to increase from 45 million tons in 2014 to 85 million by 2030, making the aquaculture industry the fastest growing animal food producing sector in the world. The European Union needs an innovative aquaculture industry to meet rising seafood</p>	WATERFORD INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	UNINOVA

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>demand and to enhance its commercial stocks. AQUASMART addresses the problem of global knowledge access, seamless data exchanges and data reuse between aquaculture companies and its related stakeholders. The AQUASMART mission is driven by the business need of the European aquaculture companies, when companies have business objectives that they cannot achieve due to lack of instruments that would enable them to manage and access to global knowledge and big data, in a multi-lingual, multi-sector and cross-border setting. Experienced research institutes, with complementary expertise and technology, participate in the consortium as technology supplier and transfer of solutions to the aquaculture stakeholders that is properly represented by important companies in the consortium. The data collected in the</p>		

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>AQUASMART open data cloud is suitable to be reused in other industrial domains if needed, (e.g., environmental or transportation data), providing a cross-sectorial setting to the provided solution.</p>		
OPTIMUM	<p>The EU-funded OPTIMUM project is working to unveil state-of-the-art information technology solutions to improve transit, freight transportation and traffic connectivity throughout Europe. Through tailor-made applications, OPTIMUM is striving to bring proactive and problem-free mobility to modern transport systems by introducing and promoting interoperability, adaptability and dynamicity. OPTIMUM establishes largely scalable architecture for the management and processing of multisource big data, which enables the continuous monitoring of transportation system needs while facilitating proactive decisions and actions in a semi-automated way. The project</p>	INTRASOFT INTERNATIONAL S	UNINOVA

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>follows a cognitive approach based on the big data supply chain loop “Observe, Orient, Decide, Act”, with the aim of achieving continuous situational awareness. Among other things, OPTIMUM aims to: - capitalise on the benefits and potential of big data fusion and proactive behaviour in the context of diverse and multimodal transportation by designing a distributed and scalable architecture;- enable comprehensive observations of the transport ecosystem by designing and developing a smart sensing system able to cope with huge amounts of heterogeneous data in real time (Observe);- enable semantic understanding of acquired data and predict the status of transport networks for short- and medium-term horizons by designing and developing an efficient management framework for dynamic (proactive) and context-aware forecasting and</p>		

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	<p>the detection of situations of interest on the basis of complex and predictive data analysis algorithms and event detection (Orient);- support proactive decisions and sustainable transportation behaviours through proactive information provisioning and personalisation (Act);- realise sustainable transportation behaviours through system-aware optimisation mechanisms that integrate adaptive charging and crediting models and real-time multimodal routing and navigation algorithms (Decide);- deploy proposed solutions in real-life pilots to place challenging use cases in the domain of the proactive improvement of transport system quality and efficiency — such as proactive charging for freight transport and Car2X communication integration; and- enable the provision of suitable business models for the commercialisation of results beyond selected end-user pilots to</p>		

Project	Main Research Area	Coordinator	Contact/Partner Involved
	ensure the impact of the OPTIMUM approach.		
ESSNet Big Data	ESSnet Big Data is a project within the European statistical system (ESS) jointly undertaken by 22 partners. Its objective is the integration of big data in the regular production of official statistics, through pilots exploring the potential of selected big data sources and building concrete applications.	National Statistics of Netherlands	Ms. Christina Pierrakou

Table 2-11: Linked projects

3 Monitoring and Evaluation of Dissemination and Communication Activities

A set of monitoring and evaluation measurements that measure and evaluate the dissemination and communication activities of the project have been determined. Table 3-1 below lists all the measurements determined for the 1st period

Measurement Type	Success criterion
Number of attended events	10
Number of events with project's presentation	7
Number of conference papers	5
Number of journal papers	1
Number of articles in industry magazines	4
Number of industry contact points	50
Number of industry communities informed about the project	5
Number of webinars	1
Number of internal partners' events	5
Number of links to the project's website	15
Number of project's presentations in standardisation meetings (online or offline)	3
Number of press releases	4
Number of project's factsheets / brochures and banners	5
Number of e-Newsletters	5
Number of blog posts in EC mechanisms	3
Number of workshops organised	4
Number of projects with synergies	5
Number of joint activities	4
Number of working groups	3
Number of unique visitors	2000
Average duration of Visits (min)	2
Number of page Views	5000
Number of accumulative followers in social media	375
Number of accumulative posts	500

Measurement Type	Success criterion
Number of interactions	125
Number of posts in website	25
Number of interactions	50

Table 3-1: Monitoring and evaluation measurements

4 Standardisation plans

In this section, we describe the standardisation groups and bodies that are relevant to the BigDataOcean project. The BigDataOcean partners will continuously seek opportunities to participate and if possible contribute to standards that are linked with the activities of the project. Although the project is at its very early stage, a standardisation workshop that the BigDataOcean partners are planning to join has been identified and is being presented in subsection 4.2.1. As the project evolves, it is expected that BigDataOcean outcomes will have impact on the standards and the BigDataOcean partners are committed to contribute the project's findings to the related standardisation bodies or groups.

4.1 Identification of related standardisation bodies

4.1.1 W3C Semantic Statistics Community Group

This community group aims to be a forum for the statistics community and the Linked Data community to examine issues arising from applying semantic technologies in the statistical production process and to report on best practices in the use of statistics on the Web of data. In particular, the group aims to discuss use cases of the application of the Data Cube vocabulary in the production of official statistics and establish if there is a need for more standardisation of vocabularies to ensure comparability of statistics data on the Web of Data.

Members of official statistics agencies and other government bodies that produce data (e.g. administrative, geospatial, government funded research results), statisticians, researchers and anyone in the Web of Data community who is interested in the publication of statistical data that can lead to statistical analysis of the maximum rigour may potentially be part of this group. It should be noted that this group will not publish specifications.

4.1.2 OGC/W3C Spatial Data on the Web Working Group

The mission of the Spatial Data on the Web Working Group is to clarify and formalise the relevant standards landscape. In particular, the group will determine the way spatial information can best be integrated with other data on the Web and how machines and people can discover that different facts in different datasets relate to the same place. It will also identify and assess existing methods and tools and then create a set of best practices for their use. Finally, it will complement the standardisation of informal technologies already in widespread use.

4.1.3 Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)

The OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) is an international not for profit organisation committed to making quality open standards for the global geospatial community. These standards are made through a consensus process and are freely available for anyone to use to improve sharing of the world's geospatial data.

OGC standards are used in a wide variety of domains including Environment, Defence, Health, Agriculture, Meteorology, Sustainable Development and many more.

OGC members come from government, commercial organisations, NGOs, academic and research organisations.

4.1.4 NIST Big Data Public Working Group

The NIST Big Data Public Working Group (NBD-PWG) was established together with the industry, academia and government to create a consensus-based extensible NIST Big Data Interoperability Framework (NBDIF) which is a vendor-neutral, technology- and infrastructure-independent ecosystem enabling Big Data stakeholders (data scientists, researchers, etc.) to utilise best available analytics tools that will process and extract knowledge through the use of standard interfaces between swappable architectural components. The NBDIF is being developed in three stages/phases with the goal to achieve the following, with respect to the NIST Big Data Reference Architecture (NBD-RA):

- Identify the high-level Big Data reference architecture key components, which are technology, infrastructure, and vendor agnostic;
- Define general interfaces between the NBD-RA components with the goal to aggregate low-level interactions into high-level general interfaces and produce a set of white papers to demonstrate how NBD-RA can be used;
- Validate the NBD-RA by building Big Data general applications through the general interfaces.

4.1.5 ISO/IEC JTC 1 WG9

Information Technology includes the specification, design and development of systems and tools dealing with the capture, representation, processing, security, transfer, interchange, presentation, management, organisation, storage and retrieval of information. JTC 1 is the standards development environment where experts come together to develop worldwide Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) standards for business and consumer applications. Additionally, JTC 1 provides the standards approval environment for integrating diverse and complex ICT technologies. These standards rely upon the core infrastructure technologies developed by JTC 1 centres of expertise complemented by specifications developed in other organisations. WG9 of JTC 1 is working on standards related to Big Data

4.1.6 CEN/CENELEC

The European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC) are two distinct private international non-profit organisations based in Brussels. Their mission is to fulfil the needs of their stakeholders: amongst others business, industry and commerce, service providers, public authorities and regulators, academia and research centres, European trade associations and interest groups representing environmentalists, consumers, trade unions as well as small and medium enterprises, and other public and private institutions. They aim to produce high-quality standards for products and services that incorporate quality, safety, environmental, interoperability and accessibility requirements. They adapt proactively to new developments and support European competitiveness, the protection of the environment and sustainable growth for the well-being of citizens and the strengthening of the single market (European Economic Area). They promote the unique European Standardisation System and its results, leading the implementation of best practice in standardisation around the world. Finally, they actively support international standardisation, and cooperate closely with the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) in order to pursue the goal of 'one standard, one test, accepted everywhere'.

CEN/CENELEC consider transport as an important player in the economy with many European companies being world leaders in infrastructure, logistics and manufacturing of transport equipment

and traffic management systems. Thus, as expected, standardisation activities cover classical transport modes (rail, road, maritime) and horizontal issues such as interoperability, intermodal transport, intelligent transport systems and transport of dangerous goods.

4.2 Plans for participation to standardisation and regulation meetings

4.2.1 CEN Workshop on Big Data

In conjunction with the IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Innovation (IEEE ICE conference) a CEN workshop on Big Data is organised at Madeira Island, Portugal on 27th of June 2017. BigDataOcean partners are planning to join the workshop, present the BigDataOcean project and establish communication channels with CEN.

5 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented a snapshot on the status quo of the dissemination, communication and standardisation efforts within the BigDataOcean project. Furthermore, the deliverable provides a detailed description of the dissemination and communication strategy the BigDataOcean consortium plans to follow in the forthcoming 15 months of the project to achieve wide promotion of BigDataOcean outcomes and to convince the society and the industry to embrace and adopt the introduced solutions. The purpose of this dissemination plan is to make the high-quality work items of BigDataOcean available to a wider audience through many different dissemination activities.

It is worth mentioning, that although the project is at its early stage, considerable efforts that increase project's visibility and raise awareness to the relevant stakeholders have already been made by BigDataOcean. BigDataOcean partners have organised 4 workshops, one per pilot, inviting stakeholders to establish communication links with them and identify their requirements out these pilots. Furthermore, project's representatives have participated in Big Data PPP Info Days Networking event and joined Big Data Value Association, where the plan is to actively participate and promote project's outcomes during the project's lifecycle.

The dissemination strategy adopted by BigDataOcean, in compliance with the Technical Annex descriptions, facilitates the dissemination of BigDataOcean work through its own website and communication channels in social media (i.e., Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn), where users can find news about the evolution of project work and all the relevant information. Such information include the submission and publication of the technological concepts and results achieved by the project in high quality selected journals, magazines and book chapters, contributions and participation in international conferences, workshops and summits characterised by high h-index and low acceptance rate, organisation of training events, seminars and hackathons, as well as organisation of BigDataOcean workshops that ensure the promotion of project's work to a wide audience.

Finally, a set of standardisation bodies that are relevant to the project have been identified and planned standardisation activities have been presented.